

Innovations Aftermath the Untold Story of Bhopal Gas Disaster

– A Prayer for Rain

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Abstract

On 2-3 December 1984, the world's worst industrial disaster took place in Bhopal, India. The villagers were sound asleep as methyl isocyanate (MIC) gas leaked from a nearby pesticide plant owned by Union Carbide India Limited. The deadly gas spread and killed at least 4,000 people, while causing significant morbidity and premature death for thousands more. Even after nearly 35 years, the aftermath of the tragedy continues to haunt villagers in the area, physically and psychologically. The present paper aims to introduce the Bhopal gas tragedy and the learning outcomes from the disaster. The aftermath of the tragedy is that we are blessed to have Environment Protection Act of 1986 and for the claims another act was passed by the Parliament-The Bhopal Gas Leak Disaster (Processing of Claims) Act, 1985 which was enacted on 29th March 1985. Prior to this tragedy till 1984, there was no central legislation related to the environment. The tragedy dealt with certain laws like Public Liability Insurance Act of 1991 and Factories Act of 1948. Chemical Safety and Hazard Investigation Board (CSB). The ultimate goal of CSB is to use the lessons learned and recommendations from its investigations to achieve positive change within the chemical industry—preventing incidents and saving lives.

Keywords: Bhopal, MIC, Union Carbide, disaster, industrial safety, risk management, security standards, industrial regulations.

The Bhopal gas tragedy

On the evening of 02 December 1984, operators began routine maintenance activities in the factory owned by **Union Carbide India Limited (UCIL)**. Washing of pipes was performed to keep a filter system clean by flushing contaminants out with water. It will never be possible to know exactly how water reached a tank of a highly reactive pesticide intermediate², but the most widely accepted theory is as follows:

One of the overflow devices downstream from the filter was blocked. Water began to flow back into the vent system through a leaking isolation valve. Water could not have flowed so far if the safety procedure had been followed, whereby a slip blind is installed to achieve an impenetrable seal between the pipes.

Water travelled through hundreds of metres of pipes from the filter, eventually reaching storage tank E-610 containing 42 tonnes of **methyl isocyanate (MIC)**¹. The pressure gauges connected to the tank were ignored as operators presumed the gauge to be faulty. Also, there was no reliable way of monitoring the tank temperature. The pressure of the tank was supposed to be maintained at a certain level with inert gas to prevent backflow into the tank. However, there was an undetected leaky valve connecting the tank to the plant's main pipe system. If gas could get out, then water could get in.

A chemical reaction between MIC and water began and heat was generated. The reaction mixture inside the tank progressively warmed as conditions moved closer to a thermal runaway reaction. The tank should have been kept cool with a refrigeration system, which had been switched off months earlier. Soon, the thermal runaway reaction took place. Hot MIC vapour burst through the tank’s automatic pressure relief system and started to escape through the dysfunctional vent gas scrubber, which was meant to neutralise toxic gas exhaust from the plant. When the operator finally noticed the actual condition inside the tank, it was already too late to stop the catastrophic loss of process containment. At this point, nothing could have been done to stop the release.

The deadly gas drifted downwind into surrounding communities, causing the death of thousands of residents of Bhopal, leading to what is known as the world’s worst industrial disaster, the Bhopal gas tragedy. The sequence of events leading to the occurrence of the disaster are illustrated in Figure 1. It should be noted that if any of the safety measures (in green boxes) had been functioning properly, the incident could have been prevented.

Figure 1–Series of failures leading to the Bhopal gas tragedy

Learning outcomes

Several lessons learned are presented. They can be applied to other industries to strengthen an organisation's defence mechanism against failures.

Asset integrity & reliability

Equipment and instrumentation failures are summarised as follows^{3, 4}:

- the refrigeration system was turned off
- pressure gauge was thought to be faulty, hence its readings were ignored by the operators
- tank temperature was not logged
- the MIC storage tank was not pressurised due to a leaky valve
- the tank's high-temperature alarm was not functioning
- vent gas scrubber (VGS) was under maintenance
- VGS could not handle the large influx of MIC even if it were in operation
- the evacuation tank E-619 was not empty
- iron pipelines were allowed to corrode
- water curtains which were 10 metres high were not tall enough to reach the stack of VGS which was 30 metres high
- flare tower was disconnected from the plant pipe system
- many valves, vent lines and feed lines were in poor condition.

Mechanical integrity programs ensure the design, installation and maintenance of equipment are fit for use from when they are fabricated to their retirement. It involves three approaches to properly address design, operational and technical deficiencies, which include:

- plan and implement preventive, predictive, proactive and corrective maintenance procedures to maintain equipment integrity
- provide proper training to each worker in terms of process overview, hazards and maintenance procedures
- inspect, test, correct and record any defects that are outside acceptable limits on a timely manner.

Inherently safer design (ISD)

The UCIL plant reacted methylamine with phosgene to produce MIC, which was then reacted with 1-naphthol to produce the fertiliser product carbaryl. The process involves the formation of the intermediate compound, MIC, which is very hazardous. Inherent safety should have been applied in hazard management⁵. Inherent safety approach is a concept of avoiding hazards at source instead of controlling them. The four main approaches and some example actions which could have been done were listed as follows:

1. Minimise, or use small quantities of hazardous substances:

-reduce hazardous MIC intermediate inventory as it is not essential as a raw material nor a product

-keep incompatible materials apart and avoid water for washing or any other purposes.

2. Substitute, or replace hazardous reactions with another of less hazard:

-use a safer route by reacting alphanaphthol and phosgene to produce chloroformate ester, followed by reaction with methylamine to yield carbaryl to avoid MIC formation, regardless of higher operating costs.

3. Moderate, or reduce the strength of an effect:

-separate UCIL plant location from potentially impacted people, evacuation points and emergency response facilities

-store MIC in several smaller tanks instead of two big concentrated ones.

4. Simplify, or eliminate unnecessary complexity to reduce risk of human error:

-design equipment to totally contain MIC at ambient temperature or the maximum attainable process temperature.

If engineers adopt inherent safety in their plant designs, risk control would not be so dependent upon regulation, operator training, protective systems and so on.

Process Hazard Analysis (PHA)

Starting from the UCIL plant formulation stage itself, hazard assessment had not been highlighted by the company nor the local authority in evaluating the certainty of potential rare events in complex facilities. At the corporate level, the major errors include not evaluating the feasibility and safety levels of a toxic facility close to a railway station and centre of population. At the governmental and regulatory level, the

errors include permitting the construction of the MIC plant amidst the local community without assessing the potential hazards, or reviewing the risk as people started building houses close to the factory.

Thus, a rigorous process hazard analysis which identifies, evaluates and controls hazards involved in a process should be adopted to anticipate the catastrophic potential of a toxic facility and to make necessary prevention and mitigation strategies. A comprehensive PHA must at least address process hazards, engineering and administrative controls, consequences of deviation and steps required to correct or avoid deviation.

Pre-Startup Safety Review (PSSR):

Pre-startup safety review (PSSR) is a way to identify, evaluate and control issues proactively before an activity is given the permission to proceed. If thorough checking and isolation on MIC storage lines are enforced before washing, the accident could have been prevented. PSSR shall confirm that prior to the operation of critical activities, the criteria below are achieved:

1. Equipment are in accordance with permissible design specifications.
2. Adequate safety, operating, maintenance and emergency procedures are in place.
3. Process hazard analysis has been resolved.
4. Training of each employee involved in an operation has been completed.

Employee participation

As a part of an economy drive, the period of safety training on site was reduced from six months to 15 days. Manpower in safety and maintenance was also cut down intensively to save costs. This substandard system indirectly brought about the tragedy due to the operators' poor perception of risk severity, neglecting specific instructions, giving orders without comprehending the nature of task, failure to communicate and not taking efficient corrective measures⁴. The previous minor accidents were indicative of eroded operator performance beyond minimum compliance in a highly hazardous plant. Hence, employee participation in decision making, resources of knowledge and planning and implementation of safety measures

in a reasonable manner is of utmost importance. An employee involvement program may include regular training and performance assessment to ensure their competency level, developing and reviewing of operating and maintenance procedures and incident investigations.

Human error prediction & rectification

To address human errors caused by slips, lapses or mistakes, the possibility of failure affected by different **error producing conditions (EPC)** should be considered to varying degrees.

Through quantitative assessment of each factor that is potentially relevant to the situation, **human error probability (HEP)** can be estimated. Before any operations, the **human error assessment and reduction technique (HEART)** should be employed to assess whether the calculated HEP is acceptable or not and if corrective actions are needed to reduce the likelihood of errors. To formulate the most cost and time effective error reduction strategies, sensitivity analysis can be further used to pinpoint the factors that have the greatest effect on error probability.

Leading & lagging indicators

The next level of management errors in the accident were system related errors, which included:

- Negligence on earlier minor MIC leakages or 'near misses' that caused burns and deaths.
- Failure to improve after earlier inspection that reported concerns on leaks of phosgene, MIC and chloroform, ruptures in pipework and sealed joints, defective gauges and indicators and unsatisfactory instruction methods.

To evaluate how well a facility is functioning, leading and lagging indicators should be used to measure performance gaps between current and desired performance precisely. A leading indicator such as a safety audit is proactive monitoring that examines the effectiveness of a facility through routine and systemic inspection and provides an early warning of potential incidents. A lagging indicator, such as accident investigation, is result-oriented. It keeps track of undesired events to measure compliance with safety rules.

Emergency response planning (ERP)

Corporate management has an undeniable responsibility in establishing proper emergency response procedures which serve as the last layer of defence to reduce the consequences in cases of loss of control. Some prerequisites for an effective ERP which UCIL failed to deliver before, during and after the incident include:

-Before leakage — potential airborne hazards, toxicity of emissions and treatment methods in case of accident were not disseminated. There was no knockdown tank to direct discharged MIC to flare tower.

-During leakage — Ad hoc response by operators was prone to errors as severe stress hindered rational decision- making.

-After leakage — Delayed and less noisy warning alarm that could not be heard outside the factory, lack of evacuation routes and late information delivered to police officials and hospitals for treatment due to lack of detailed rehearsal of emergency with active involvement of all management levels.

The essence of ERP includes preparedness, response and recovery as a strategy to minimise injury, property and public damage and to provide immediate resumption of normal operations. The three main components of ERP include:

Prevention — identify credible scenarios and assess operating procedures and safety measures.

Internal and external communication — share information with site emergency responders and neighbouring communities.

Mitigation — internal emergency planning and cooperation with external services.

Safety as a prime concern

Analysis of the Bhopal accident indicates all human initiated catastrophe can be traced back to management failures. Yet these inadequacies are often poorly tackled as production or financial targets are always the major concern along with simultaneous loss and slipping of knowledge and expertise. As it is hard to analyse the probabilities of undesirable events in a complex system accurately, the status of safety management and compliance to regulations at both corporate and governmental

levels has to be high. For this, a sense of preparedness and open-mindedness has to be stimulated and equipped to diminish the risks of occurrence of detrimental events.

Lesson learnt and recommendations

Several lessons can be learnt by analyzing this accident. Occurrence of this accident triggers the importance of safety management measures and also elucidates a minor change can lead to major consequences. The safety study committee, safety review committee and industrial safety division were appointed and created to identify major hazards and to study and review the requirement or availability of protection system and safety plant.^{6,7} The committee visited all installations and made recommendations for improvement of safety. Industrial safety regulations were revised. Industrial plant safety division advises generic industrial safety issues, recommends measures on industrial safety for prevention of accidents and providing guidance on the overall planning for prevention and protection. They also conduct review of the safety documents being developed on industrial safety. Industrial and fire safety review is created. They prepared a checklist for safety audit and carry out detailed study and assessment of the safety programme. The audit is required to be carried out by persons focusing on specific requirement, depending on the hazard potential of plant operation.

Occupational health and safety review and Advisory committee on occupational health are created to advise on occupational health aspects (Occupational Safety Manual BHEL).^{8,9} Including implementation of statutory provisions, occupational disease etc. Fatal accident assessment committee to assess fatal accidents and to arrive at the root causes of accident and preventive actions to be taken to avoid recurrence. Safety professional meetings are conducted to hold workshop at the individual units to discuss statutory requirements and their implications and to conduct a seminar on industrial safety. Safety awards for the industries are provided by the ministry of labor and employment for industrial safety excellence. The safety performance assessment based on computed value of safety numbers, preventive efforts and hazards as per a pre-defined computational methodology. Data's are collected in standard formats every year from all the industries for assessment of safety measures. Safety color

codes^{10,11} are introduced to identifying the physical hazards and expediting fire fighting operation and other emergency services. Consider the fire prevention fighting (Red), machineries causing injuries (Orange), general caution (Yellow), first aid and personal protective equipments, e.g. - gas masks (Green), radiation hazards (Purple), housekeeping and traffic locations (Black and White) and caution or warning against starting equipment under repair e.g. -lifts (Blue).

Management techniques

Poor design of the gas scrubber, flare tower, water curtain and along with poor maintenance standards leads to this major disaster.¹²⁻¹⁵ Other countries and industries also created awareness, education, training and capacity development of mitigation and better preparedness to initiate industrial safety and disaster management. This disaster also paved a way to reliability, availability, maintainability and safety criterion importance to follow the effective management techniques¹² like **sole system hazard analysis (SSHA)**, **hazard operability studies (HAZOP)**, **preliminary hazard analysis (PHA)**, **interface hazard analysis (IHA)** and **operating and support hazard Analysis (O&SHA)** to study about hazards. **Quantitative risk analysis (QRA)**, **risk analysis (RA)**, **management oversight risk tree analysis (MORT)**, **probabilistic risk assessment (PRA)** and comprehensive risk management plan to analyze risks.

Safety assessment is done by systems plan (SSP), **safety critical item list (SCIL)**, **design safety review (DSR)**, **operational safety report (OSR)** and safety audit. **Failures modes effects and critical analysis (FMECA)**, **THERP** and, **fault tree and event tree analysis (FTA AND ETA)** and **fire explosion and toxicity index (FETI)** for analyzing, modeling, monitoring, predicting the root causes of the disaster and preventing the risk and ensuring safety. Thus the business environment imperative to quantify their damage potential through computerized modeling results, identify hazards in plant operation and then remedial measures are practiced for risk minimization and control. They also increased their quality assurance activities (the management system built to ensure safety systematically) by safety preservation inspections.

Metrics recommended

Fatal Accident Rate (FAR) and **Potential Loss of Life (PLL)** are the commonly used metrics to avoid any risks.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ FAR gives the expected number of fatalities per 100 million working hours. Potential loss of life is just the expected number of fatalities associated with certain activities, without taking the exposure, such as the number of person at risk or the exposure time, into account and often based on historical statistics. Unlike PLL, FAR takes exposure time into account. Probability of **failure on demand (PFD)** and **Risk reduction factor (RRF)** (1/PFD) are the quantitative measure for safety. Metrics for individual risk is calculated by **Individual risk per annum (IRPA)** which gives the probability that a specific individual will suffer a fatal accident during a year. SSI risks are higher as compared to big industries because of improperly designed facilities, untrained manpower. The key to combat industrial disasters management during emergency is through proper emergency preparedness.²⁰ The government strengthened legislative provisions with regard to the sites of establishment of industries, relocation etc. Regulatory bodies should not work with a stick in hand but should work on a partnership basis (with the industries) and the approach should change effectively that persuade industries for self-regulation.

Industries should be encouraged to adopt new management tools such as ISO 9000, ISO 14001 etc. Management in small and medium scale sectors in which four significant causes will trigger safety. They are adequate process risk evaluation, adequate engineering to cope up with likely deviations, process demands and human factor. The safety measures in chemical and polymer industries includes developing EHS management systems (OSHAS 18000 and ISO 14000 certifications), safety audits during pre commissioning and post commissioning stages of the plant. They also depend on training programs for employees on PPEs, lead poisoning, equipment safety, HAZOP, conveyor safety, conduction work zone monitoring (RSPM, Noise and Heat) and developing safe operating procedures for all equipments inside the plant will prevent future disasters.

Conclusion

Thus the present scenario is in whatever position beyond debates and arguments, the rate and the magnitude with which accidents are affecting human lives; looks inevitable that the future may have lot to pay to galloping industrialization/liberalization.¹⁶ Multiple factors led to many eventual disasters and explosions. But the major root cause of the problem was the corporate cost-cutting techniques/methods, failure to invest in safety infrastructure and finally lack of safety culture to the employees/workers. “Time present and time past and both perhaps present in time future and time future contained in time past”. Therefore the perspectives of disasters in the past will be best suitable vision to visualize the present and future industrial safety. Demand in industrial safety standards and safety planning, and threats about risk were the lesson learnt from this entire catastrophic event. The good news is that we know what to do and now we just have to do it because a little care makes accident rare. Thus emergency planning and safety management system be the tool to minimize the disasters like Bhopal in future. A good safety management system do everything right up to 99.99% and 0.1% becomes untoward incidence. This 0.1% needs to be focused now.

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